

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
Conservation genomics in the age of extinction	Recording (YouTube video)	Recording of the live webinar presentation	Available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://youtu.be/laei-9Gu-AI
Taylor_Slides	Slides (PDF)	PDF copy of the slides presented during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record